

Two-Dimensional Electron Gas with 100% Spin- Polarization in the (LaMnO₃)₂/(SrTiO₃)₂ Superlattice under Uniaxial Strain

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Abstract : By first-principles calculations we investigate the structural, electronic, and magnetic properties of the (LaMnO₃)₂/(SrTiO₃)₂ superlattice. We find that a monoclinic C_{2h} symmetry is energetically favorable and that the spins order ferromagnetically. Under both compressive and tensile uniaxial strain the electronic structure of the superlattice shows a half-metallic character. In particular, a fully spin-polarized two-dimensional electron gas, which traces back to the Ti 3d_{xy} orbitals, is achieved under compressive uniaxial strain.

Keywords : manganite, strain, 2DEG, superlattice

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